

1 Cellular degeneration and genomic instability.

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7 We studied total transcription in induced pluripotent stem cells of patients with a lysosomal storage
8 disorder, Niemann Pick Disease, to describe the basis of a relationship between cellular degeneration and
9 genomic instability. Cells manifested loss of MDC1, the mediator of DNA damage checkpoint 1 and
10 activation of the geminin DNA replication inhibitor GMNN. Cells displayed activation of NEAT1
11 concomitant with induction of chromodomain helicase DNA binding proteins *CHD3* and *CHD5*. Cellular
12 degeneration phenotypes can have significant consequences on genomic stability involving DNA
13 replication dynamics and helicase function.

14 Citations

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